

CAUSATIVE CONSTRUCTION OF *PEU-* AND *SEU-* IN ACEHNESE LANGUAGE

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Abstract:

This article deals with causative construction which discusses the Causative marker **Peu-** and **Seu-** in Acehese, the goal of this is to describe several facts and data of using causative marker **peu-** and **seu-** in Acehese. The source of the data is a native Acehese community in several cities in Aceh Province. The data of this study were obtained through field linguistic methods which included direct elicitation, recording, and checking elicitation. Furthermore, the research instrument used in this study is a list of questions, Distributional methods applied in analyzing research data based on the problems discussed in this article. The results of data analysis showed that the causative construction of *peu-* and *seu-* are different morphosyntactically, it could be seen from the word category, the causative markers of *peu-* can be attached to verbs, adjectives, nouns, pronoun, and numerals, whereas *seu-* only to be attached to verbs, noun (*seu-neubab*) and adjectives. whereas based on semantic parameters the different of meaning occurred if *peu-* dan *seu-* attached to intransitive verbs of *manoe*, *musom*, etc. and the prevalence and unusual/mark-unmark categories found if *peu-* and *seu-* attached to several transitive and intransitive verbs, while if *peu-* and *seu-* attached to adjectives also have different meanings such as attachment to the adjective *miyub*, *malèè* and *matèè*.

Keywords : causative, *peu-*, *seu*, Acehese, valency

1. Introduction

The Discussion of Acehese sentence construction is an appealing subject matter to be discussed as it is built with *peu-* and *seu-* as the causative markers, for its function had a mechanism of valency change with an argument structure to be examined. In addition, the term of valence was closely related to verb cause the predicate was filled with verbs that could increase or decrease the valency.

The mechanism of valences change of the Acehese verbs includes a discussion of verbal construction, namely causative, applicative, and resultant constructions. This article focuses on studying of the causative marker *peu-* and *seu-* in Acehese Language. It is known that causative construction based on formal parameters (morphosyntaxis) are lexical causative, morphological causative, and analytical causative.

This article is aimed to answer the question of how the causative construction of *peu-* and *seu-* marker in Acehese was formed. The objective of this article was to provide the knowledge, particularly the causative construction of Acehese language, it would be expected to enrich typology in linguistics demand. This article focused on the efforts to get a deeper finding and insight of *peu-* and *seu-* construction based on morphosyntactic and semantic parameters in Acehese language.

The Analyzing of Causative construction was very instrumental in linguistics field, many expert not only take a chance from a typological aspect, but also examined the phenomenon based on the convergence of linguistics and philosophy (natural causation), and cognitive anthropology (human perception and causation categories) (Comrie 1989: 165).

2. Concept and Framework

The term of valence in linguistics refers to the ability of verbs, which occupies the predicate element of a sentence to bind an argument. Valency refers more to the number of arguments needed by verbs that occupy predicate positions.

2.1 Causativity

Each language has different causative constructions from one another. There are languages that have all three types of constructs (lexical, morphological and analytic) and also languages which only have two types of causative constructs; lexical and analytic causative.

Goddard (1998: 266) states that causative construction is an expression which contains an event caused by someone's actions or cause something to occur. The discussion about causative construction are expressed by Artawa (1995: 48), which reveals that almost every language has a unique way of forming or expressing causative construction. Commonly, causative describes a macro-complex situation that contains two micro situations or events consisting of (1) the cause (*causee*) that causes an event to occur (causing event) and (2) the event that occurs or results arising (*caused*) caused by actions caused (*causee*) (Shibatani 1976: 239, Comrie, 1989: 330, and Song, 2001: 253)

The real condition showed that each language has a different grammatical construction from one another to express causative construction. However, in cross-language, the equality of causative construction could be expressed syntactically and analytically.

Artawa (1998: 32) states that one of the main syntactic differences between non-causative constructs and causative constructs lies in the increased valence of verbs in

causative construction. The study of verb valency changes caused by the causativity and focused on the difference in valence of non-causative verbs which include intransitive verbs, transitive verbs, and ditransitive verbs. The relation between causative construction and non-causative construction is explained through the hierarchy of grammatical relations of the *subject* > *direct object* > *indirect object* > *oblique object*. In the hierarchy of grammatical relations, it is explained that *causee* occupies the highest position, namely the left position which is the position of the causative argument that has not been filled (Comrie, 1989: 342).

Language that has all three types of construction is generally agglutinated as this type has affixes that could be attached to verb which function to increase or decrease the valence of verb. Meanwhile, languages that only have two causative types are isolation type as they generally do not have affixes to increase or decrease the valency of verb.

3. Theoretical Framework

As mentioned previously, based on formal parameters (morphosyntax), Comrie (1981: 158--160; 1989: 165--171) states that causative construction are divided by causative analytic, morphological causative, and lexical causative. Based on three causative construction proposed by Comrie (1981: 158--160; 1989: 165--171), Acehnese language has analytic, morphological and causative lexical causative construction. While causative based on semantic parameters, Comrie (1989: 171) focuses on true causative and permissive causation (permissions)

Mayani (2005: 243-247) create causative maps based on causative parameters in Madura language both with affixation and causative verbs. The semantic features listed by Mayani (2005) are intentional elements by adding "intentional" adverb to causative construction.

Comrie (1989: 165) states that every causative situation will involve two components of a situation or event, *cause* and *effect*, it is in line with Shibatani (1976: 1) and Goddard (1998: 266) who argue that causative is a situation occurs on two interconnected events, one showing the cause and the other declaring the effect. Whereas Dixon (1998: 1) considers that causative is a transitive process, this is quite reasonable that causative markers can convert intransitive to transitive.

This transitive has an effect on changing the number and syntactic function of the arguments of a sentence.

- 1) "*the bus fails to turn up*" as the result in (02)
- 2) "*I am late for the meeting*" Comrie (1989:165)

The Sentence (01) it can be explained that "the bus fails to turn up" as a causee, which results in a sentence (02) I am late for the meeting as a result. According to Comrie (1989), the two causes and effects on the previous statement are two types of micro situations, which combined together become a macro-situation, which is a causative situation.

The macro situation will be natural if the two sentences above are combined into "the bus's failure caused me to be late for the meeting" or the bus didn't come so I was late for the meeting " we often encounter this expression between micro situations and the macro situation, so that we can shorten the sentence into a causative form of "the bus caused me to be late."

This is the basic concept of causative situations form based on the analysis of the situation stated by Comrie (1989), the micro situation and the macro situation illustrated in the form of a chart by Purwiati (2012), which is:

The Acehnese language morphosyntactically has lexical causative construction, morphological construction and analytic / periphrastic construction; as shown by some examples below:

- | | |
|----------------------------|--|
| Morphological construction | : <i>duek</i> 'to sit' → ' <i>peu-duek</i> 'to seat' |
| Analitical construction | : <i>gèt</i> 'good' → ' <i>peu-gèt</i> 'make, create, renew' |
| Lexical construction | : <i>plén</i> 'switch off' → ' <i>geu-plén</i> 'to make it switch off' |

The three types of causative in Acehnese language, indicates the existence of a causal component which is displayed explicitly from *duek* 'to sit' to be '*peu-duek* 'to seat', *gèt* 'good' becomes '*peu-gèt* 'make, create, renew' and *plén* 'to make it switch off', all of the causativity presents the core argument as the *causee* and consequence of increasing verb valences that can be seen from two micro situations of causative construction as the macro situation, which in Acehnese is displayed in one event.

This study was limited to the construction of causative markers *peu-* and *seu-* (affixes) in acehnese, , where *peu-* and *seu-* affixes not included in the lexical causative category in the Acehnese language, and it was only aimed to describe the causality of Acehnese typologically, namely morphological causative and analytical causative construction as morphosintaxis parameters and semantic parameters, as *peu-* and *seu-* were considered to be a marker of *causee* found in the case of Acehnese languages.

4. Discussion

4.1 Acehnese Causative Construction of Morphosyntax Parameter

Analitical Causative of *peu-* and *seu-* in Acehnese

Analytical Causative is also called pherifrastic causative. This type had a predicate that expresses *causee* and *caused*, the *causee* was expressed by a separate word from the word that indicates *caused* (effect). The Predicates in analytical causative were manifested in separate predicates and characterized by the presence of verbs with had causative

meaning *gèt* 'good' *yue* 'order' and *jeut* 'to be'. The accusative verbs *gèt* 'good', *yue* 'order' and *jeut* 'to be' are verbs used in Acehnese analytical construction. The use of the verbs are shown below.

- (03) Adoe i-moe.
Younger sibling 3-cry
My brother is crying.
- (04) Leman *i-peu-gèt* adoe i-moe.
Name 3-Caus-make younger sibling 3-cry
Leman made little brother crying
- (05) Leman *i-peu-gèt* i-moe adoe
Name 3-Caus-make 3-cry younger sibling
Leman made a crying brother
- (06) Haris *i-peu-gèt* kursi
Name 3-Caus-make chair
Haris made a chair
- (07) Haris *i-peu-jeut* kayèè keu kursi
Name 3-Caus-make wood prep-to chair
Haris made wood into a chair
- (08) Mawar geu-taguen bu.
Name 3-cook rice
Mawar cooks a rice
- (09) Mak geu-*yue* mawar taguen bu.
Mother 3-Caus- name cook rice
Mother told mawar to cook a rice.

The data above showed us the changes in non-causative construction, both construction with intransitive verbs (03 and 06) and transitive verbs (08), become causative construction in (04, 07 and 09) by requiring the presence of *get*, *jeut*, and *yue*. The presence of this causative verb caused these constructions had two predicates in each construction. The impact of adding this causative verb is the addition of arguments that function as *causee*. The verb *get* in (04) requires the presence of *leman*, the verb *jeut* in (07) demands the presence of *haris*, and the verb *yue* in (19) requires the presence of *mak*. The presence of *leman*, *haris*, and *mak* indicated as *caused*. *Leman* causes *adoe* to cry, *Haris* causes *kayee* 'wood' to be a chair, and *mak* causes *mawar* to cook a rice. The accompanying predicate of the causative verb *gèt* 'good' can also be adjectives and nouns, as follow:

- (10) Rumoh nyan lagak that.
House dem beauty very
The house is very nice.
- (11) Amir *i-peu-gèt* rumoh nyan gèt that lagak.
Name 3-Caus-make house dem good very beauty
Amir built the very nice house

The analytical causative showed us the tendency that its construction was not formed solely as of the causative verb role, but the structure form of the argument in

the causative verb also played an important role. The role of the argument from this analytical causative structure can be seen from the non-acceptance of construction (05).

Based on the structure of the forming argument, the analytical causative construction in Acehese consists of [NP-VPCaus-NP-VP/AdjP.] while the causative that formed from the intransitive verb consist of NP-VPCaus-NP-VP. The structure of the argument [NP-VPCaus-NP-VP-NP], and the causative originating from the transitive verb with the structure of the argument [NP-VPCaus-NP-VP-NP].

The presence of *causee* arguments in (04, 07, 09, and 11) as the results that the subjects in non-causative constructions become direct objects, *adoe* 'younger sibling' in (03), *kursi* 'chair' in (06), *mawar* 'name' in (08), and *rumoh* 'house' in (10) become object when attached to *peu-moe* (04), *peu-jeut* (07), *yue* (09), and *peu-gèt* (11). The changes of this function caused of the subject function filled by *causee* argument.

4.2 Morphological Causative in Acehese

In general, the affixes as causative markers in Acehese are *peu-*, and *seu-*. It could be seen from the word category, The causative markers of *peu-* can be attached to verbs, adjectives, nouns, and numerals, whereas *seu-* only to be attached to verbs and adjectives.

Causative *Peu-* and *Seu-* and its derivational construction

The meaning of intransitive verb *manoe* 'to take a bath' in (12a) can be expressed by the affixation of the causative morpheme *peu-* and *seu-* to its intransitive form *manoe* in *peu-manoe* (12b) and *seu-manoe* (12c), the sentences of morphological causatives are as shown below:

(12a) Kak nah *geu-manoe*

Name 3sg bathe

Kak Nah takes a bath

(12b) kak nah ka *geu-peu-manoe* *adoe* lôn bunoe

Name perf-3sg 3-caus-bath younger.sibling 1sg just now

Kak Nah bathed my younger brother just now

(12c) Kak nah ka *geu-seu-manoe* *adoe* lôn bunoe

Name perf-3sg 3sg-caus- bath younger. sibling 1sg just now

My sister bathed my younger brother just now

The causative *peu-* had a wide range of derivative forms. It could be attached to a verb, a noun and adjective, and numeral but causative *seu-* only used in limited cases of morphological causative due to the common use of Acehese structure. There are differences of using *peu-* and *seu-* which will be discussed subsequently.

The causative attachment of *peu-* as in (12b) and *seu-* in (12c), showed the addition of argument structure with increasing valency level of the intransitive verb *manoe* 'bath' be transitive when attached to *peu-manoe* and *seu-manoe*. The effect of adding causative affixes *peu-* and *seu-* were the addition of arguments that function as *causee*, while the verb *manoe* 'bath' was the result that causes *adoe manoe* 'younger brother takes a bath' from these two micro situations to be a macro situation in the two

causative sentences. Morphologically, the causativity of *peu-* and *seu-* in Acehnese could be derived from several word classes, including:

4.3 Morphological Causatives Derived from Verb

Causativity and causative construction of Acehnese generally occurs in transitive and ditransitive clauses.

Derived from an unaccusative intransitive verb

Rheut 'to fall down' → *peu-rheut* 'to cause to fall'

- (13a). *böh u nyan rheut dari bak u.*
Fruit Coconut Dem Perf-fall prep-from tree coconut
'The Coconut fell from coconut tree.'

- (13b). *böh u nyan i-peu-rheut le buw dari bak u*
Fruit Coconut Dem Perf-3-Caus-fall by monkey from tree coconut
'Monkey caused the coconut to fall from the coconut tree.'

Derived from an transitive verb

Jéb 'to drink' → *peu-jéb* 'to make drink'

- (14a). *Marni geu-jéb ie .*
Name 3sg drink water
'Marni drinks water.'
- (14b) *Marni geu-peu-jéb (keu) Hani ie .*
Name 3-Caus-drink to Name water
'Marni makes Hani drink a water.'
- (14c). *Marni geu-peu-jéb ie (keu) Hani .*
Name 3-Caus-drink water to Name
'Marni makes Hani drink a water.'

Derived from adjective

Lagak 'beautiful' → *peu-lagak* 'to make beauty'

- (15a) *moto dewi lagak.*
Car Name beautiful
'Dewi's car is beautiful.'
- (15b). *Dewi geu-peu-lagak moto gobnyan.*
Name 3-Caus-beauty car s/he
'Dewi beautifies her car.'

There are several other forms which are causative processes derived from adjective in the Acehnese language, such as:

- *itam* 'black' → *peu-itam* 'blacken/discolour'
- *mameh* 'sweet' → *peu-mameh* 'sweeten'
- *reuloh* 'broken' → *peu-reuloh* 'to ruin'
- *bereh* 'okay' → *peu-bereh* 'to tidy up'
- *lheueh* 'finished' → *peu-lheueh* 'to finish'
- *gleh* 'clean' → *peu-gleh* 'to clean up'
- *taloe* 'lost' → *peu-taloe* 'to beat'
- *karu* 'noisy' → *peu-karu* 'to disturb'

Derived from noun

Lamiet 'slave' *peu-namiet* 'to make like slave'

(16a). Jih awak lamiet .

3sg person slave

'He is a slave.'

(16b). kah ka *peu-namiet* droe keuh.

2sg perf-2 Caus-being enslave 2sg

'you are being as a slave.'

payông 'umbrella' *peu-payông* 'to wear the umbrella'

(17a). pat ka kubah payông ?.

where perf-2sg keep umbrella

'where did you keep the umbrella ? .'

(17b) mak lon geu-*peu-payông* adoe dari ujeun.

Mother 1sg 3-caus-umbrella younger.sibling from rain

'my mother covers the younger sister/brother from the rain.'

Rincông 'crease/ceremonial knife' *peu-rincông* 'use rincông as the device of creese'

(18a). pat ka pueduk rincông?.

where perf-2sg keep rincông

'where did you keep the rincông? .'

(18b) gobnyan geu-*peu-rincông* pancuri.

He 3sg 3-caus-crease(rincông) thief

'He is use the rincông to kill the thief.'

Lamiet → *peu-namiet* in (16a) and (16b), *payông* → *peu-payông* in (17a) and (17b), and *rincông* → *peu-rincông* in (18a) and (18b) are examples of the causative processes derived from nouns based on morphological parameters, in this case *Lamiet* → *peu-namiet* and *rincông* → *peu-rincông* are rarely used and not so popular in that as there is no system of slavery at the moment, using the word *tob* 'to pierce' is more popular for acehnese people rather than *rincông* → *peu-rincông*, whereas *payông* → *peu-payông* is still often used in daily conversations. There are several other forms which are causative processes derived from nouns in the Acehese language, such as:

- *Nan* 'name', → *peu-nan* 'to name'

- *Sira* 'salt', → *peu-sira* 'to add salt'

- *saka* 'sugar' → *peu-saka* 'to add sugar'

- *tapak* 'footprint' → *peu-tapak* 'to kick'

- *beude* 'rifle' → *peu-beude* 'to shoot'

- *utang* 'debt' → *peu-utang* 'to lend'

- *ngen* 'friend' → *peu-ngen* 'to accompany'

- *seubab* 'cause' → *seu-neubab* 'to cause'

The most appealing thing to discuss is the causative process derived from nouns *seubab*, "cause", While *seubab* 'cause' in Acehese language is the only one of noun can be attached by *seu-*, The causativity will raise the valency of verb and become a macro situation by two micro-situation when *seu-* attached to *seubab* 'cause', as seen in (19a) as *causee*, (19b) as *caused* and (19c) as *macro-situation*.

- (19a) kah ka rhom manok nyan ngen batee
You 2-perf hit chicken dem with stone
You hit the that chicken with the stone
- (19b) manok nyan matée
chicken dem die
the chicken died
- (19c) kah *seu-neubab* manok nyan matée.
you 2-caus-cause chicken dem die
You caused that chicken died

The Sentence (19a) can be explained that *kah ka rhom manok nyan ngen batee* 'hit the chicken with stone' as a *causee*, which results in a sentence (19b) *manok nyan matée* 'the chicken died' as a *caused*. (19a) and (19b) indicated the causativity of two micro-situation which raising the valency of verb, by adding the argument of actor, the two causes and effects in (19a) and (19b) are two types of micro-situations, which combined together become a macro-situation which is a causative construction as in (19c) as *kah seu-neubab aneuk manok nyan matée* 'you caused that chicken died'.

Derived from numeral

- *Duwa* 'two', → *peu-duwa* 'make to be two'
- *Peut* 'four', → *peu-peut* 'make to be four'

Derived from pronoun

- *Kah* 'you', → *peu-kah* 'make to call as you'
- *Adeun* 'big brother', → *peu- aduen* 'make to call as big brother'

Derived from *jeut* 'be' and *get* 'good'

As previously explained, in essence, the causativity is a process of increasing verb valency by adding the argument of agent/actor which is also the cause of the occurrence. *Jeut* and *get* can be attached to the causative markers in the language of Aceh.

Jeut 'be' → *peu-jeut* 'to be'

- (20a). lôn jeut keu urueng syik.
1sg be parent
'i am being a parent.'
- (20b). lôn ku-*peu-jeut* tivi nyan udép lom.
1sg 1sg-Caus-be television dem on again
'I make that television turn on again.'

get, good, → *peu-get* 'to make/to create'

- (21a). rumoh nyan ka gèt.
House dem perf-good
'that house is nice.'
- (21b). lôn ku-*peu-gèt* rumoh nyan .
1sg 1-caus-make house dem
'I built that house.'

Commonly, the Acehnese causativity applied in monotransitive verbs. Most of monotransitive verb contains causative meanings, such as verb *matée* 'die'. The

application of each monotransitive verb in causative construction of Acehnese is presented as follow.

- (22a) Tikôh matéé
Rat die
the Rat dies
- (22b) samiun *geu-peu-matéé* tikôh nyan
Name 3sg-caus-die rat dem
Samiun kills that rat

4.4 Semantical Parameter of Acehnese Causative Construction

Causative analysis based on semantic parameters should be done for causative construction with affixation and causative verbs, semantically would display similar but had no same meaning, when we attached the affixes *peu-* and *seu-* to intransitive verbs, adjectives and numerals, both of them are different in terms of meaning, and the chance of use between *peu-* and *seu-* were not same, although both of them could increase the verb valence in causative construction.

There were several significant differences in the pattern of using causative construction with affixes *peu-* and *seu-*, as follow:

- *Peu-* dan *seu-* attached to intransitive verb *manoe* 'take a bath'

- (23a) Kak nah *geu-manoe*
Name 3sg bathe
Kak Nah takes a bath
- (23b) kak nah ka *geu-peu-manoe* adoe lôn bunoe
Name perf-3sg 3-caus-be bath younger.sibling 1sg just now
Kak Nah bathed my younger brother just now
- (23c) Kak nah ka *geu-seu-manoe* adoe lôn bunoe
Name perf-3sg 3-caus-be bath younger.sibling 1sg just now
My sister bathed my younger brother just now

(23b) and (23c) showed us the different meaning semantically of using causative *peu-* and *seu-*, which is attached to the intransitive verb *manoe* 'to take a bath', *peu-* which attached to the verb '*manoe*' in (23b) is carried out with the element of coercion, whereas *seu-* in (23c) 1c was carried out to work on the *manoe* 'take a bath' without coercion. The causativity of in semantic term of *seu-* could also be carried out by the *seu-manoe* action as of the inability of *adoe* 'brother' to bathe on their own, for reasons of being a baby or as *manoe*'s action was carried out on people who are sick.

In some cases of Acehnese language, the transitive process does not necessarily make *seu-* parallel with *peu-* which can be attached to each intransitive verb to increase the valence of the verb. The causative *Peu-* commonly used compared to *seu-*, for they had different semantic functions, as in the example mentioned above.

There are several mark and unmark of using *peu-* and *seu-* that attached to intransitive verbs as follow:

Table 1: Mark and Unmark of using *Peu-* and *Seu-*

Intransitive	Attached by <i>Peu-</i>	Note	Attached by <i>Seu-</i>	Note
<i>beudöh</i> 'to wake'	<i>Peu-beudöh</i> 'to wake up'	Unmark	<i>Seu-beudöh</i> 'to wake up'	Mark
<i>éh</i> 'Sleep'	<i>Peu-éh</i> 'put to sleep'	Unmark	<i>Seu-éh</i> 'put to sleep'	Mark
<i>dông</i> 'Stand'	<i>Peu-dông</i> 'to stand up'	Unmark	<i>Seu-dông</i> 'to stand up'	Mark
<i>hu</i> 'to turn on'	<i>Peu-hu</i> 'to switch on'	Unmark	<i>Seu-hu</i> 'to switch on'	Mark
<i>meulho</i> 'fight'	<i>Peu-meulho</i> 'to bring into fight'	Unmark	<i>Seu-meulho</i> 'to bring into fight'	Mark
<i>teubit</i> 'to go out'	<i>Peu-teubit</i> 'to pull out'	Unmark	<i>Seu-teubit</i> 'to pull out'	Mark
<i>woe</i> 'to go home'	<i>Peu-woe</i> 'to return'	Unmark	<i>Seu-woe</i> 'to return'	Mark
<i>tamông</i> 'to enter'	<i>Peu-tamông</i> 'to get in'	Unmark	<i>Seu-tamông</i> 'to get in'	Mark
<i>reubah</i> 'to fall'	<i>Peu-reubah</i> 'to knock down/to break down'	Unmark	<i>Seu-reubah</i> 'to knock down/to break down'	Mark

There are several mark and unmark of using *peu-* and *seu-* that attached to transitive verbs as follow:

Table 2: Mark and Unmark of using *Peu-* and *Seu-*

Transitive	Attached by <i>Peu-</i>	Note	Attached by <i>Seu-</i>	Note
<i>ék</i> 'up/to climb'	<i>Peu-ék</i> 'to raise'	Unmark	<i>Seu-ék</i> 'to raise'	Mark
<i>Hah</i> 'to open'	<i>Peu-hah</i> 'to open up'	Unmark	<i>Seu-hah</i> 'to open up'	Mark
<i>Meu-reuno</i> 'to learn'	<i>Peu-reuno</i> 'to teach'	Unmark	<i>Seu-reunoe</i> 'to teach'	Mark
<i>Bloe</i> 'to buy'	<i>Peu-bloe</i> 'to sell'	Unmark	<i>Seu-bloe</i> 'to sell'	Mark
<i>Meu'èn</i> 'to play'	<i>Peu-meu'èn</i> 'to hold a child/person walking around'	Unmark	<i>Seu-meu'èn</i> 'to hold a child/person walking around'	Mark

There are also verbs below which are marked for *peu-* and are unmarked to *Seu-*.

Table 3: Mark and Unmark of using *Peu-* and *Seu-*

Transitive	Attached by <i>Peu-</i>	Note	Attached by <i>Seu-</i>	Note
<i>Pula</i> 'to plant'	<i>Peu-mula</i> 'to farm'	Mark	<i>Seu-mula</i> 'to farm'	Unmark
<i>Pajoh</i> 'to eat'	<i>Peu-majoh</i> 'to make someone eat'	Mark	<i>Seu-majoh</i> 'to make someone eat'	Unmark
<i>Patéh</i> 'obedient'	<i>Peu-matéh</i> 'to obey'	Mark	<i>Seu-matéh</i> 'to obey'	Unmark
<i>Piké</i> 'to think'	<i>Peu-miké</i> 'to make someone think'	Mark	<i>Seu-miké</i> 'to make someone think'	Unmark

There are verbs below which are unmarked for *peu-* and *Seu-*.

Table 4: Unmark of using *Peu-* and *Seu-*

Verb		Attached by <i>Peu-</i>	Note	Attached by <i>Seu-</i>	Note
<i>Meusom</i> 'to hide'	Intransitive	<i>Peu-meusom</i> 'to hide'	Unmark	<i>Seu-meusom</i> 'to hide'	Unmark
<i>Beud</i> 'recite'	Transitive	<i>Peu-beud</i> 'to teach to recite'	Unmark	<i>Seu-meu-beud</i> 'to teach to recite'	Unmark

The case of the prevalence of the use of *peu-* and *seu-* as a causative marker in Acehese also occurs in affixes which attached to transitive verbs, for example:

- (24a) *lôn ku beud al qur'an*
1sg perf recite Koran
I am reciting Koran
- (24b) *Gurèè geu-peu-beud lôn al qur'an*
Teacher 3-caus-recite me Koran
The Teacher teaches me to recite Koran
- (24c) *Gurèè geu-seu-meu-beud lôn al qur'an*
Teacher 3-caus-afix-recite me koran
The Teacher teaches me to recite Koran

Morphologically, the causative *peu-* and *seu-* in (24b) and in (24c) above, both are commonly used in each conversation, where the *seu-* is the *causee* of the action *beud* 'recite' as a result of the overall macro-situation, the difference between the two causative *peu-* and *seu-* is in the necessity for the presence of affix *meu-* which attached to the transitive verb *beud* 'to recite' to complete the role of causative *seu-*, if the *seu-* used without affix *meu-* as *seu-beud*, then the situation is unusual, and the use of affix *meu-* which attached to *peu-meu-beud* is unusual too. Both are actually balanced and commonly used, while the use of *seu-meu-beud* is considered to be more subtle in the category for teacher actions in teaching the Koran, as well as dialect differences from several regions in Acehnese.

To compare the affixes *peu-* and *seu-*, you should also see the following example:

- (25a) *kah ka musom i likot rumoh*
2sg 2-hide at back house
You hide behind the house
- (25b) *lôn ku peu-musom peng i-miyub peuratah éh*
1sg 2-caus-hide money at-under bed
I hide the money under the bed
- (25c) *kah seu-meusom ata nyan bak lôn*
2sg caus-hide thing dem from i am
You hide something from me

The causative marker of *Peu-* which attached to intransitive verb *meusom* 'hide' in (25b) semantically had a different meaning from affix *seu-* which attached to intransitive verb *meusom* 'hide' in (25c), although the affixes *peu-* and *seu-* were the *causees* of the emergence of causativity in the macro situation of intransitive verb *meusom* 'hide', as the result in an action of hiding something, as of the *causee* *peu-meusom* / *seu-meusom* 'to hides'. *Peu-* and *seu-* produced two arguments in (25b) and (25c), but the argument structure of *peng* 'money' is something concrete and clearly being hidden, and the use *seu-* is attached to the intransitive verb *meusom* 'hide' was intended for core / object arguments had not been concrete.

Aside from the attachment of *peu-* and *seu-* to intransitive and transitive verbs, the differences in semantic functions are also occurring as a causative process inherent in adjectives. As follow:

- (26a) *ubông rumoh nyan miyub*
Roof house dem low

the roof of that house is low

(26b) Bang Lah ka *geu-peu-miyub* ubong rumoh

Name perf3sg 3-caus-be lower roof house

Abang Lah had lowered the roof of the house

(26c) Mayet nyan i-*seu-miyub* bak rumoh

corpse dem 3-caus-be lower at house

The corpse was placed at home

Semantically there is a different meaning of using *peu-* and *seu-* which is attached to the adjective *miyub* 'lower', *peu-* which is attached to *miyub* 'lower' in (26b) carried out with the meaning of 'making low', while *seu-* in (26c) is an action of place the corpse or the process of laying the corpse inside before the procession of bathing of corpse in accordance with the faith of the Islamic adopted by the majority of Acehnese. The impact of the addition of the causative affixes *peu-* and *seu-* is the addition of the argument that serves as the *causee* *peu-* and *seu-* attached to the adjective *miyub*, whereas adjective *miyub* in (26b) becomes the result that caused the 'roof of the house to be low' and *miyub* in (26c) caused the corpse to be placed inside the house 'as a macro situation.

The Comparison can be seen to the following sentence.

(27a) lôn malèè keu kah

1sg ashamed to you

I am ashamed of you

(27b) kah ka *peu-* malèè lôn

2sg 2-caus-ashame me

You embarrass me

(27c) Buet kah ka *seu-* malèè urueng chik kah

Job your perf2-caus-ashame parent your

your job embarrassed your parents

Peu- was attached to adjective *malèè* 'ashame' in (27b) had different semantic meaning from *seu-* that was attached to the adjective *malèè* 'ashame' in (27c), although *peu-* and *seu-* are the *causee* of the emergence of causality in macro situation from adjective *malèè* 'ashame' which a results in action of 'ashame' as of *peu-* *malèè* / *seu-* *malèè* 'embarrassing'. *Peu-* in (27b) indicates the meaning of 'intentional' as the cause of *lon* '1sg/i' being embarrassed, whereas *seu-* was attached to the *malèè* 'ashame' in (27c) did not indicate intentionally was making his parents ashamed, but there was an action that indirectly made parents shy.

To look at the balance of the causative markers of Acehnese, it can be seen in the following example:

(28a) rumoh lôn barô

House my new

My new house

(28b) gobnyan ka *geu-peu-barô* rumoh lôn

He perf3sg 3-caus-new house 1sg/my

He was renewed my house

(28c) gobnyan ka *geu-seu-barô* rumoh lôn

- He perf3sg 3-caus-new house 1sg/my
The man renewed my house
(29a) manok nyan ka matéé
Chicken dem already die
The chicken died
(29b) gobnyan geu-*peu-matéé* ulee nyan
He 3-caus-die snake dem
The Person kills the snake
(29c) gobnyan geu-*seu-matéé* uleue nyan
He 3-caus-die snake dem
The Person kills the snake

Peu- and *Seu-* affixes in (28b) and (28c) are attached to the adjective *barô* 'new' as well as (29b) and (29c) which are attached to the Adjective *matéé* 'dead', both have the same semantic meaning and are balanced, there is no difference semantic meaning in the use of both, even though the frequency of the using *peu-* which is attached to the adjective *barô* 'new' more often used compared to *seu-*. *Peu-* and *seu-* indicates that there is an act of *peu-barô* or *seu-barô*, *peu-matéé* or *seu-matéé* as the *causee* of the house becoming new, the snake is dead. *Rumoh barô* 'new house' and *uleue matéé* 'snake died' are the consequences of the actions of *peu-barô* / *seu-barô* and *peu-matéé* / *seu-matéé*.

5. Conclusion

To create the causative construction of *Peu-* and *Seu-* in Acehnese can be done in several ways, *peu-* can be attached to intransitive verbs, noun, adjective, numeral, and pronoun, whereas *Seu-* can be attached to some intransitive and transitive verbs such as *manoe*, *eh*, *döng*, *pula*, *pateh*, *pajoh* etc and attached to adjectives such *barô*, *matéé*, *malèè*, etc. *Seu-* also can be attached to noun *seubab* as the macro situation of two combining micro-situation. *Peu-* and *Seu-* are prefixes in Acehnese as causative construction marker that played an important role in increasing the valence of verbs.

The semantic parameter of causativity in this article could explain the difference of meaning in some cases in Acehnese. This may begin with a verb distribution and an adjective which form a macro situation from the entire *causee* and *caused* process. It is done to substitute the causative verb in a wider construction. It appears that the limits of the ability to substitute synonymous forms, for example in certain constructions can replace each other and in other constructions cannot replace each other.

References

- Alsina, A. and Joshi, S. 1991. *Parameters in Causative Constructions*. Chicago Linguistics Society 27
Artawa, Ketut. 1994. *Ergativity and Balinese syntax*. Melbourne: PhD thesis: La Trobe University, Melbourne.

- Artawa, K. 1995. "Teori Sintaksis dan Tipologi Bahasa". Makalah yang dimuat dalam Jurnal *Linguistika*. Tahun II edisi 3. Denpasar: Program Studi Magister Linguistik Univ. Udayana
- Artawa, K. 1998. *Ergativity and Balinese syntax* (Parts 1, 2, and 3). NUSA Linguistic Studies of Indonesian and Other Languages in Indonesia, volumes 42, 43, 44. Jakarta: Badan Penyelenggara Seri NUSA. xv + 169 pp
- Azwardi. 2018. *Ilmu Bahasa Aceh*. Banda Aceh: Bina Karya Akademika
- Comrie, B. 1981. *Language Universals and Linguistic Typology*. Oxford: Basil Blackwell.
- Comrie, B. 1985. Causative Verb Formation and Other Verb Deriving Morphology' dalam T. Shopen et.al (ed) *Language Typology and Syntactic Description* Vol. 309-348. Cambridge University Press
- Comrie, B. 1989. *Language Universal and Linguistic Typology*. Oxford: Basil Blackwell.
- Dixon, R. M. W. 1994. *Ergativity*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
- Durie, Mark. 1985. *A Grammar of Acehese On the Basis of a Dialect of North Aceh*. Dordrecht : Foris Publications.
- Goddard, C. 1998. *Semantic Analysis : A Practical Introduction* . Oxford: Oxford University Press
- Goddard, Cliff. 1998. *Semantic Analysis – A Practical Introduction*. Oxford : Oxford University Press.
- Haspelmath, M. 2002. *Understanding Morphology*. London: Arnold.
- Mayani, L.A. 2005. *Konstruksi Kausatif dan Aplikatif Bahasa Madura*. Tesis. Denpasar: Program Studi Magister Linguistik Universitas Udayana.
- Mayani, Luh Anik. 2005. Konstruksi Kausatif Bahasa Madura. *Jurnal Linguistik Indonesia*. Volume 23 Nomor 2. 237-249
- Purwiati, Ida Ayu Mirah. 2012. Sistem Konstruksi Kausatif Bahasa Bali. *Widyaparwa*. Volume 40 No. 1. 69-78
- Shibatani, M. (ed.). 1976. *Syntax and Semantics: The Grammar of Causative Construction*. New York: Academic Press, Inc.
- Song, Jae Jung. 2001. *Linguistic Typology: Morphology and Syntax*. London: Longman

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